

UNLOCKING THE URBAN CODE

A photographic catalogue of Digital Social Innovation in Turin and Rome

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Unlocking the Urban Code

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In the last decade, a wide variety of social innovation initiatives performed through digital processes, supported by digital tools, and realised in the digital space have been experimented, implemented, scaled up and uptaken in worldwide cities (Certomà & Corsini 2020). Depending on the intentions and interests of the activists, innovators, hackers or makers promoting them, these are labelled as digitally-enabled social innovation, digital innovation for society, tech4good, social tech, civic tech and similar. We adopted Digital Social Innovation (DSI) as the label that better conveys the social orientation toward emancipatory intervention.

The concept of DSI has been mainly popularised in the European Research and Innovation domain to refer to a broad and diversified domain of initiatives through which communities of innovators (whose intentions range from strengthening, reforming or even subverting the neoliberal institutions that support the capitalist system) adopt digital technologies (i.e. the technologies using digital infrastructure and relying on digitisation processes) and internet connectivity to advance knowledge and solutions that tackle with a wide range of social needs (e.g. employment, welfare, care services, environmental quality...) (EC, 2013; 2014). Therefore DSI practices refer to heterogeneous, multiscale and multitemporal collective practices, supported by the diffusion of

digital connectivity devices and networks, incorporated in socio-technological systems that allow the establishment of novel organizational modes of social life. From enabling participation in public mapping, planning or decision-making, to crowdsourcing ideas for solving shared problems, designing or providing local services, or enabling online civic initiatives, DSI encompass place-based and context-specific initiatives and bear a strong relationship with the urban space.

As a matter of fact, with the advent of the digital revolution, both the concept and the experience of the urban space underwent profound changes; and the physical dimension of the city merged with the virtual one, endowed with a new organisational logic (De Wall, 2015). This produces new spatialities (Graham, 2011), i.e. new constructions of collective imaginary emerging from the social encounter with space mediated by digital tools and processes.

In the PRIN2022 MUR project “Digitally-enabled Social Innovation in the City. Implications for Urban Spaces, Societies and Governance”, we analyse the reasons underlying this trend and explain how the analysis of spatial implications of DSI can bring novel exploratory insights around the thematic nodes of representation, reproduction and power (Certoma’, 2023).

The city seems to offer the necessary conditions for implementing DSI initiatives, by its relative compactness and density, combined with a high level of connectivity, and a comparatively higher level of social acceptance of new projects, which is often accompanied by a propensity to experiment with spontaneous, citizens-led, socio-ecological answers (Evans, Karvonen, 2010; Corsin Jimenez, 2014) to the economic and financial crises that cyclically manifest as functional stage for the reproduction of the global capitalism. Notably, in their understanding of the digitally-mediated city, critical geographers engaged with the theorization of the relationship between digital technologies and the production of space (Thrift & French, 2002; Dodge&Kitchin, 2008; Leszczynski, 2015).

The “augmented urban space” (De Cindio&Aurigi, 2008) emerges as the effect

of the pervasive changes in the material-semiotic of the city due to the digital revolution, and changed the way in which society reproduces and represents its own space. De Cindio and Aurigi clarify that: “There are no entirely digital lifestyles [...] yet at the same time most lifestyles are digitally-enhanced, in many different as well as subtle ways. In the augmented city, ‘virtual’ and ‘physical’ spaces are no longer two separate dimensions, but just parts of a continuum, of a whole. The physical and the digital environment have come to define each other and concepts such as public space and “third place”, identity and knowledge, citizenship and public participation are all inevitably affected by the shaping of the reconfigured, augmented urban space” (2008, p.1). At the same time, digital processes are never entirely immaterial, as most of the DSI processes show by tightly connecting with the geographical context of realisation (Verona et al., 2006; Goodchild, 2007). Building upon Edward Soja’s classification of space, the material infrastructures and immaterial space of codes and connections are adjunct to the physical space in the constitution of the "first space", while the "second space" of geographical representation and multiple connections emerge from the density of communications infrastructures. The "third space", recalled by De Cindio and Aurigi in the definition of the augmented city, is generated from the assembling of multi-scalar socio-techno-environmental networks and makes cities able to harness tangible and intangible resources (Landry, 2015) - because “when cities are combined with digital technologies, our urban habitat becomes the most sophisticated technology for interaction ever created” (Han and Hawken, 2018, p.2). Therefore the virtual space of a city can be regarded just as a continuation of the city around, inside, beyond, and behind its physical space. It is in the “augmented urban space” that DSI emerges. The following photographic work represents the third space together with the heterogenous, material, embedded and embodied practices that make it possible. Notably, the photographic exploration allows us to appreciate an often-underestimated aspect of DSI, i.e. the physicality of digital technologies in the local context and daily performances. This way, the photographic lens is not merely a documentation tool, but a heuristic one, able to disclose new dimensions of the phenomenon.

While the digital revolution seemed to confirm the annihilation of space (Harvey, 1989) as the ultimate effect of postmodern virtualization, this photographic collection suggests something different. It shows that DSI processes also produce an expansion of relational space in which heterogeneous networks operate. These changes in the spatiality and the space of the augmented city include transformation of reproductive practices, social routines, collective imagination, political visions, and place where processes happen on multiple scales.

The shots allow us to engage with the issue creatively and redefine the meaning of urban space in the digital time, giving voices to marginalities, alternatives counter-hegemonic positions, and the divergent positions operating in the reproduction of digital capitalism.

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(FabLab Torino)**

2023

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(Mondo Digitale)**

2023

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